

THE MAIN ASPECTS OF THE INTERNATIONAL SITUATION IN THE EARLY 1990S OF THE XX CENTURY**Mammadli Shahla***PhD, senior researcher of the Institute of History named after A.A. Bakikhanov of ANAS**Baku, Azerbaijan*<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8822-3513>**Abstract**

At the end of 1991, all the republics that formed the USSR declared independence. This marked the start of a period where they had to be recognized by each other, as well as by other countries around the world. This resulted in the creation of 15 independent states that became subjects of international relations. Many countries, made up of different ethnic groups, faced a difficult challenge in the fight against nationalism. Yugoslavia broke up into several states, some of which were engulfed in intense struggles due to various reasons, including religion and ethnicity. The withdrawal of Soviet troops from Afghanistan in 1988-1989 resulted in further civil war, while the Baltic countries severed ties with the foreign policy of the USSR. In general, the United States emerged as the only superpower, with its role in global affairs increasing significantly.

Keywords: USSR, CIS, international relations, Yugoslavia, socialist republics, the USA, Europe.

During the 1990s, the international situation was characterized by the deepening of economic integration between Western Europe and North America, as well as the development of integration processes in Latin America, Southeast Asia, and Africa. However, during this same period, centrifugal processes accelerated in Eastern Europe and the USSR, and national conflicts engulfed Yugoslavia, Czechoslovakia, and the USSR. As a result, the USSR collapsed and its former republics declared independence. This led to two different processes emerging at the end of the 20th century: globalization, which involved the integration of economic relations in the capitalist world, and the process of creating national states in the countries of Central Asia, Southeastern Europe, and the former USSR.

In 1991, all the republics that were part of the USSR declared their independence, marking the beginning of mutual recognition between them and by other states in the international community. As a result, the 15 independent states that were once part of the USSR became recognized as subjects of international relations and agreed to maintain equal relations amongst themselves [1, p.103-118].

After the Declaration of Independence, the main challenge was to ensure mutual interests among the newly independent states. It is incorrect to assume that the collapse of the USSR automatically marked the end of relations between the republics. In reality, it was an aftermath of the conservative policies of the central government. The emergence of a system of independent states paved the way for the establishment of close relationships between nations based on new principles. The foundation for this process was laid at a meeting held on December 8, 1991, where the heads of Belarus, Russia, and Ukraine decided to establish the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS). The agreement stated that the union was open to all the states of the Soviet Union, as well as other countries that supported its goals and principles. These principles comprised fundamental objectives such as strengthening interna-

tional peace and security, compliance with international obligations stipulated by treaties and agreements of the USSR, and ensuring unified control over nuclear weapons and their non-proliferation.

On December 21, 1991, a meeting was held in Almaty where the heads of 11 states announced the creation of the CIS and the collapse of the USSR. The Baltic countries and Georgia did not participate in this meeting. After the collapse, all the republics joined the UN and Russia took the place of the USSR in the UN Security Council [7].

In the early 1990s, nationalism became widespread in many countries. Yugoslavia disintegrated into several countries, some of which began to struggle among themselves on religious and national grounds. The United States emerged as the only superpower and began to actively intervene in the affairs of various states, either independently or within the NATO bloc. They justified this by claiming to support universal human values while also pursuing their own interests. Many countries lacked the ability or willingness to confront the United States, and therefore only sought to defend their territory or local and regional interests.

In the first half of the 1990s, international relations were characterized by the absence of conflicts between various state associations. This allowed the United States to claim the position of world leader. However, their strategic interests led them to interfere in the internal affairs of other nations.

During this time, Russia was known for its weak foreign policy. The Russian foreign policy apparatus was unable to resist US policy, which led to Russia joining the state sanctions placed on Yugoslavia and Iraq. Additionally, the head of Russian foreign policy, A. Kozyrev, was seen as incompetent and was nicknamed "Mr. Yes." Despite being a supporter of fundamental changes in Russian foreign policy, Kozyrev failed to strengthen diplomatic relations with the CIS countries, particularly Ukraine, and instead pursued a pro-Western foreign policy [4, p.5-15]. Despite the Foreign Minister's best efforts, Russia failed to integrate

into the Western world, leading to accusations of betrayal of Russian interests. The first half of the 1990s was an incredibly eventful period, marked by the collapse of the Soviet bloc, the eruption of national wars in Yugoslavia, and the emergence and spread of Islamic fundamentalism and terrorism worldwide. The withdrawal of Soviet troops from Afghanistan in 1988-1989 resulted in further civil war, while the Baltic countries severed ties with the foreign policy of the USSR.

During the period under consideration, the United States of America played a dominant role in international relations, with the structure shifting from a bipolar to a unipolar one. The collapse of the Soviet Union had a significant impact on the configuration of international relations. The conditions necessary for the implementation of "new thinking" were no longer present. Until this point, the existence of two powerful states and two military blocs had been the primary factor in the international relations system. This had helped to maintain the bipolar structure of the world. However, with the collapse of one of these powerful states, the USSR, the conceptual project that had been developed in the late 1980s was completely destroyed.

Specialist on American countries and historian, Sergey Rogov, assessed multipolarity as a legitimate state in the international relations system. He pointed out that unipolarity is an abnormal state. After the Cold War, a well-known historian of international relations argued that the conflict between great powers will be replaced by a balance, and the interests of world political processes will intersect in this direction. The scholar observed that in the multipolar system of international relations, there is no situation that can satisfy the interests of all states included in this system. The mutual national interests of states can be either compatible or conflicting. Conflicts of interest can lead to wars, and states with parallel interests can form alliances to fight a common enemy [10, p.6-27].

It is evident that returning to a "natural" state of international relations does not provide a reason for optimism since the prolonged and stable existence of a multipolar world is extremely challenging. The disappearance of one of the powerful states from the world map does not imply the emergence of a "new world order"; it is more appropriate to refer to it as a "new world without order." This theory has been confirmed by a number of politicians and experts in the early 1990s. The world system not only stabilized but also encountered three significant issues: the aftermath of the USSR's collapse; the ambiguous role of new "centers of power" such as Germany, China, Japan (which can also include India and Brazil), and some countries in the Middle East; the conflict between the industrialized North and the West that is lagging behind in development.

The Russian opposition has expressed strong opinions regarding the multipolarity of international relations, the dangers arising from the new world, and their consequences. Criticism was mainly voiced by left and ultra-left organizations during 1992-1993. In the following years, Russia's foreign policy began to be criticized by the liberal opposition as well. Patriotic forces argued that the collapse of the Soviet Union and the dissolution of the Warsaw Pact were part of a "secret conspiracy" by the West, led by the United States.

This perspective suggests that the downfall of the socialist system had an adverse effect on the stability of the global system. Gennadiy Zyuganov claimed that the West had devised a specific strategy to deliver a devastating blow to the constitutional framework of the USSR, which was the only powerful country in the world. He argued that the West called the USSR the last and predatory empire that needed to be destroyed. The West tried to prove that the Soviet Union was not the architect of victory in World War II, but instead a copy of the fascist structure. He also pointed out that the West called for the complete destruction of the Soviet economy through rapid expansion of weapons and dividing the country from within by aggravating ethnic conflicts. He also argued that the West took over the media with the help of spies and destroyed the collective foundations of the state [6, p.4; 3, p.35-62].

During the Clinton administration (1993-2001), the US attempted to strengthen its position in the post-Soviet space and limit Russia's influence in the region. The aim was to ensure that the fall of the Soviet Union would mark the end of Russia's sole geopolitical leadership in the region [13, p.49]. To achieve this, the US pursued a policy that focused on bolstering its leadership in the world through the leadership of key regional military blocs and alliances, primarily NATO. [14, p.81].

During the course of events, the UN's regulatory role in crisis situations worldwide has gradually weakened. It is worth considering the "US National Security Strategy for a New Century" (1998) document, which outlines the United States' goals to protect its national security in post-Soviet countries. The authors of the document state that the inclusion of Russia, Ukraine, and other CIS states in the security system of the new Europe aims to increase their participation in NATO's "Cooperation for Peace" program and establish valuable cooperative relationships. Furthermore, the United States is committed to reducing the threat of nuclear war, the nonproliferation of nuclear weapons, and other weapons of mass destruction. Finally, the document states that the United States supports and strives for democratic states with market economies in the CIS integrated into the world community [12]. Based on the document analysis, it can be inferred that the US government prioritizes unrestricted access to energy resources over the industrial growth of the countries involved. Specifically, the Caspian region holds a significant level of interest for the United States.

The collapse of the Soviet Union was considered a tragic event for the countries within its reach and for Russia itself. Many experts saw this as the start of significant changes in the world, leading to a completely different geopolitical situation around Russia. It was believed that a geopolitical catastrophe had taken place, and the outcome of this change was uncertain. Academician Elgiz Pozdnyakov pointed out that the vast territories of the former Soviet Union and Europe were at the center of these changes. He believed that the dissolution of the USSR, the "system of socialism", and the unification of Germany went far beyond the conventional notions of international relations [8, p.102]. According to the hypothesis put forward by the academician, it was the dawn of a period of political disorganization and collapse. This is leading to a fundamentally new geopolitical situation emerging in Europe, Eurasia, and ultimately, the world. As a result, both Western and

Eastern European integration are no longer viable options [9, s.84].

According to an expert's analysis, the current international situation is unstable and has increased the likelihood of a new distribution of world territory, strategic borders, and resources. The United States, being the only powerful country in the world, has a favorable opportunity to enter the Eurasian geostrategic region to safeguard its interests. The primary goal of the US is to dismantle the Eurasian geostrategic monolith and prevent any state from becoming the dominant force in Eurasia. This objective was stated in the Pentagon plan created in March 1992. The main direction of the US policy was to thwart the emergence of a new competitor in the area of the former Soviet Union. This policy should be understood as an attempt by the American leadership to uphold the leading role of the United States in the world. After analyzing the modern landscape of international relations during the period under study, we can make the following generalizations:

1. The new world that has replaced the bipolar world is complex and prone to change,
2. The multipolar configuration of the world community is likely to persist for a long time,
3. It is impossible to apply multipolar rules under the hegemony of one powerful state - the United States,
4. Solving the global problems requires joint efforts of all countries,
5. National characteristics will be reflected in the foreign policies of individual states,
6. Critical analysis of the Western model in political and economic life becomes relevant,
7. The military power of countries will become the main factor in protecting national interests.

After the end of the Cold War, the world became more complex. Not only global, but also regional and internal threats emerged, and the features of new international relations became a subject of controversy. At that time, issues such as global cooperation, cooperation between leading countries, and US world leadership became topics of discussion.

Many economists have argued that the United States does not have the resources to lead the world, and that it will adjust the balances in the classical multipolar system. It was believed that the burden of a powerful state had unforeseen consequences for the USSR, and it would have the same effect for the United States. Politician and diplomat Nikolai Spassky noted that the US ruling circles understand that in the new conditions, it will be impossible to claim leadership relying only on the military-political apparatus, as was the case during the Cold War. According to the observer, the United States should build relationships in such a way that the main pressure falls on those elements in which the United States is strong [11, p.22-40].

Georgiy Arbatov, a renowned specialist in international politics, has analyzed the current situation and assessed the prospects for relations between two influential states. He highlights that although the Cold War has ended, it is too early to talk about ongoing processes in international politics that will lead to positive

changes. According to him, no country or expert is prepared for the world that exists after the end of the Cold War. Many of us are unaware of the problems and dangers that lie ahead. Due to this, no country has a long-term and well-thought-out policy, and no international situation is capable of responding to new realities. He explains that when we face a crisis like Yugoslavia, we try to use old methods to solve the situation. However, old methods are useless in solving new problems [2, p.3-12].

Many experts and politicians worldwide share the belief that no country, regardless of its power, can completely control the international system and its processes. Even in 1945, when the United States possessed political and financial influence, a formidable navy, nuclear weapons, and vast food reserves, it was unable to do so, as noted by prominent international relations scholars Viktor Kremenyuk and Alexey Bogaturov. Today, with its current economic and financial role significantly reduced, the US has even less of an opportunity to demonstrate such control [5, p.3-12].

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